

DELAMINATION TOUGHNESS OF MARINE COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Mode I delamination toughness of glass fibre reinforced polyester has been measured on laminates containing four unidirectional central layers. Testing methods and G_{IC} calculation followed the ESIS protocol for interlaminar fracture testing that was published in 1993. Results showed a large increase of G_{IC} with crack growth length over 40 mm. Values of n and Δ that are used for G_{IC} calculation have an unexpectedly large variation, particularly given the small scatter in flexural and interlaminar shear properties. Analysis showed that the variation of n and Δ follows a relationship that can be derived by equating the G_{IC} values from the experimental compliance method and the corrected beam theory. Using the relationship it was possible to reduce scatter in initiation values of G_{IC} (at the beginning of crack growth). A second method, based on crack length correction, also showed promising potential for reducing scatter in G_{IC} values, particularly for $G_{IC,prop}$ (G_{IC} for crack propagation). While more work needs to be done to support these scatter reduction methods, this paper points out the parameters that can lead to variability in G_{IC} measurements on marine composites.

INTRODUCTION

This paper is concerned with measurement of delamination toughness for the glass fibre composites that are used for marine applications. These glass fibre composites have many advantages over traditional marine materials, including weight reduction and improved corrosion resistance. The pleasure boat industry has adopted composites many years ago but many new applications, particularly offshore, are now under consideration. Mechanical properties of marine composites have been most commonly characterised in the past using flexural and short beam shear tests. However, such tests are insufficient to measure delamination resistance with confidence and more reliable test methods are required.

A protocol for interlaminar fracture testing of composites was first drafted by ESIS (European Structural Integrity Society) in 1988. It has since been revised and improved following round

robin testing including joint exercise with ASTM (American Society of Testing and Materials) and JIS (Japanese Industrial Standards group) [1]. The protocol recommends testing coupons with uni-directional fibres that have an insert film between two central layers. The insert film acts as a starting defect for the delamination tests. Force, displacement and crack length measurements are recorded during the test. Using either of two analyses: experimental compliance method, from Berry [2], or corrected beam theory [3], delamination resistance, G_{IC} (critical energy release rate for crack propagation) can be determined.

A special fibre lay-up for glass fibre composites, consisting of layers of stitched $0^\circ/90^\circ$ fibres on each side of four central layers of unidirectional fibres, was adopted for delamination testing of marine composites [4]. The unidirectional central layers were to provide environment around the crack similar to that of a unidirectional composite specimen, hence, the protocol is applicable to the specimens for delamination toughness measurement. The outer layers ensure that overall stiffness is similar to that used in practice. This approach has produced satisfactory results for a study of matrix effect on delamination toughness of the glass fibre composite [5].

One significant difference in delamination behaviour between carbon fibre composites and glass fibre composites is the amount of bridging fibres at the crack tip. Bridging fibres are formed due to debonding of one section of fibre from matrix. When one end of the section is attached to one crack surface and the other end to the other crack surface, a bridging fibre forms. For most carbon fibre composites, the bridging fibres are limited to a region very close to the crack tip. As the crack grows, the bridging fibres soon fracture and lose the capability of supporting the load. For glass fibre composites, the fibre bridging zones are often much larger and exist far behind the crack front. The large fibre bridging zone is partly due to high fracture strain of glass fibres, typically double that of carbon fibres, and partly to the large number of bridging fibres that reduce the load carried by each bridging fibre.

In this paper, we will discuss measurement of delamination toughness for glass fibre composites, in particular, the mechanisms that cause scatter in test results and ways to reduce this scatter.

EXPERIMENTAL

The glass fibre reinforced laminates used in the study were made by hand lay-up, at the IFREMER, Marine Materials Laboratory, France. The laminates have 4 layers of stitched $0^\circ/90^\circ$ fibres on each side of the central 4 unidirectional layers. The central layers represent approximately 1 mm out of the 6 mm specimen thickness. The glass fibres (P177) have a multi-compatible sizing and are mass produced for industry by the manufacturer, Vetrotex. The matrix is polyester orthophthalic resin that is commonly used for marine applications.

Flexural three point bend and short beam shear tests were performed following ISO178 and ASTM2344 standards.

Specimens were cut from the laminate using a diamond embedded slitting wheel with water cooling the specimens during the cutting. The water on the specimens was soon wiped out after the cutting. The specimens were then left in a vacuum oven overnight to ensure that the residual water introduced by the cutting was completely removed from the specimens. For the delamination resistance specimens an 8 μm thick polypropylene starting defect was included at mid-thickness, approximately 65 mm in length. Double cantilever beam (DCB) specimens of 20 mm wide were used.

Mode I delamination tests were conducted in an Instron universal testing machine (model 4505) with a testing speed of 2 mm/minute. Crack length increment was marked on the force-displacement curve for every 1 mm of crack growth in the first 5 mm and then, for every 5 mm of crack growth.

Calculation of G_{IC} used the two methods suggested in the ESIS protocol. The first method is corrected beam theory in which

$$G_{IC} = 3 P \delta / (2 B (a - \Delta)) \quad (1)$$

where P is load, δ is displacement, B is specimen width and a is the measured crack length from the edge of the specimens. Δ is a correction factor that is obtained from the negative x-axis intercept on a plot of a versus $C^{1/3}$ where C is the compliance, defined as δ / P .

The second method for G_{IC} calculation is experimental compliance method in which

$$G_{IC} = n P \delta / (2 B a) \quad (2)$$

where n is the slope of the log-log plot of compliance versus measured crack length.

Flexure modulus (E_f) can be determined using the following equation

$$E_f = 8(a - \Delta)^3 / (C B h^3) \quad (3)$$

where h is thickness of one arm of the specimen, that is, half of the specimen thickness.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

The results from flexural and short beam shear tests are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Scatter in results from flexural and short beam shear tests

	Thickness (mm)	E_f (GPa)	Flex Strength (MPa)	ILSS (MPa)
Mean	6.09	13.61	328.5	20.5
Coeff of variation %	1.6	2.1	5.2	3.6
No of specimens	20	10	10	10

It is clear from Table 1 that there is little scatter in the moduli and strength values in spite of the hand layup fabrication.

For DCB tests the G_{IC} ($G_{IC,Prop}$) as a function of crack length, R-curve, is given in Fig. 1. Since experimental compliance method and corrected beam theory yield similar G_{IC} values, only those

obtained from the experimental compliance method are shown. The figure shows that G_{IC} increases as crack grows for a length longer than 40 mm before a plateau value was obtained. It is not possible to give a single value to represent $G_{IC,Prop}$ due to the large increase of G_{IC} with crack length.

Most of the specimens tested in this study had a crack jump soon after the crack started growing from the insert film, in spite of the very thin film used (of thickness less than the diameter of a fibre). The crack jump made it impossible to measure $G_{IC,Vis}$ and $G_{IC,5\%}$ values recommended in the protocol [1].

Values of n , Δ , $G_{IC,Init}$, and modulus are summarised in Table 2. The $G_{IC,Init}$ that was calculated from the end of linearity on a force-displacement curve represents delamination toughness of the composite without the involvement of bridging fibres. The $G_{IC,Init}$ values in Table 2 varied from around 130 J/m^2 to nearly 300 J/m^2 , with a standard deviation of 53 J/m^2 . Similar large scatter was also reported for Round Robin delamination testing of carbon fibre composites [6]. Mechanisms that may cause scatter in G_{IC} values, including scatter of n and Δ , fibre bridging, and incorrect crack length measurement, are discussed below.

It is also important to note that the calculated moduli values in Table 2 are much higher than measured values (Table 1). This is because the assumption for eqn 3 that neutral axis of the specimens under bending is located at the center of cross section is not valid for the DCB specimens used in this study. It should also be noted that certain scatter exists in the moduli values.

Fig. 1 R-curves for the glass fibre composites

n AND Δ

The key parameters for G_{IC} measurement are n and Δ , for the experimental compliance method and corrected beam theory respectively. The two methods use crack-length-dependent compliance functions that were modified from the following equation:

$$C = k a^3 \tag{4}$$

where k is a constant depending on material properties and specimen geometry [7].

For the experimental compliance method, the following equation is used for the compliance function:

$$C = k' a^n \tag{5}$$

For the corrected beam theory, it is

$$C = k'' (a + \Delta)^3 \tag{6}$$

where k' and k'' are also functions of material properties and specimen geometry.

Curve fitting was used to generate curves from the experimental data that satisfy the two equations. Values of n and Δ were then obtained from the curves, with which G_{IC} can be calculated using eqns 1 and 2.

Table 2 Summary of delamination test results

Specimen #	Experimental Compliance Method		Corrected Beam Theory		
	n	$G_{IC,init}$ (J/m ²)	Δ	$G_{IC,init}$ (J/m ²)	Modulus (GPa)
1	2.76	267	-9.3	255	22
2	2.67	159	-10.1	155	25
3	2.72	180	-9.9	173	24
4	2.86	190	-6.0	183	20
5	2.76	200	-8.3	193	18
6	2.94	133	-2.1	131	17
7	2.64	184	-11.6	177	25
8	2.62	291	-14.6	274	25
Average (#1-#8)	2.75	200	-9.0	193	22
Average (#1-#7)	2.77	188	-8.2	181	22

The n and Δ were often used as an indicator to check reliability of the delamination test results, especially the n value for experimental compliance method. For commonly used carbon fibre composite specimens the n value is usually found to be approximately 2.7, reduced from the beam theory of 3 by transverse shear and imperfect beam end conditions. In the beginning of the study, it was therefore expected that n values of approximately 2.7 would be obtained; however, as shown in Table 1, the values varied from 2.6 to close to 3. Such variation alone can cause scattering of G_{IC} up to 10%. For the results in Table 2, we speculate that the variation in n is not the main cause of G_{IC} scattering. This is supported by results for specimens 3, 4, and 7 that have quite different n values, yet the corresponding G_{IC} values are very close.

A plot of n as a function of Δ is given in Fig. 2. The figure shows clearly that when n approaches 3, Δ approaches 0. Such a trend can be expressed mathematically using eqns 1 and 2 by assuming that these two equations give the same G_{IC} value. The mathematical expression is:

$$n \Delta = a (3 - n) \tag{7}$$

Values of Δ predicted from eqn 7 are also given in Fig. 2. The predicted Δ values are slightly higher than those measured experimentally, suggesting that the corrected beam theory gives more conservative values than the experimental compliance method. This is consistent with the experimental results for carbon fibre composites [6].

Results in Fig. 2 indicate that difference between the experimentally measured Δ value and that predicted from eqn 7 is biggest for specimen #8 (n equal to 2.62). By excluding its G_{IC} from mean value calculation, we can reduce standard deviation from 53 J/m² to 42 J/m², ie the coefficient of variation (CV) drops from 27% to 21%. If the value for specimen #1, that also has a large difference between the measured and predicted Δ values, is excluded as well, the standard deviation of G_{IC} is reduced to 24 J/m² (CV 12%) without much change of the mean value (182 J/m²). Since Δ becomes small when n approaches 3, difference between the predicted value and the measured value also becomes small. This makes it difficult to judge whether its G_{IC} should be excluded from the mean value calculation. Therefore, this technique would be more effective for scattering reduction if the specimens have similar n values.

FIBRE BRIDGING

The fibre bridging is a well recognised mechanism that increases $G_{IC,Prop}$ [8]. Since the values strongly depend on the amount of bridging fibres locally at the crack tip, the bridging fibre is also a source for scatter in $G_{IC,Prop}$.

Fig. 2 Δ plotted as a function of n.

Fibre bridging zone in glass fibre composites is often of the order of 10 to 20 mm that is considerably larger than that seen in carbon fibre composites. The bridging fibres make the section of the specimen that contains bridging fibres stiffer in a bending mode, hence increasing total stiffness of the specimen in delamination testing. The increase of stiffness depends on size and number of bridging fibres. Therefore, the increase of stiffness due to bridging fibres can vary as crack grows. This variation gives an additional parameter that can cause scattering of n and Δ values.

A composite beam model that consists of two sections, one having a larger modulus than the other, has been used to simulate the effect of bridging fibres on stiffness increase of the specimen. To simplify the mathematical derivation, it is assumed that before the fibre bridging zone is developed eqn 5 with n equal to 3 is the governing equation for compliance as a function of crack length. We also assumed that bridging fibres cause a uniform increase of bending modulus in the section that contains the bridging fibres. When a bridging fibre zone is developed, the n value decreases

from 3, due to stiffness increase in the section containing the bridging fibres. Through a simple mathematical derivation, we obtained

$$n = \log (L_1^3 + 3 L_1^2 L_2 / E^* + 3 L_1 L_2^2 / E^* + L_2^3 / E^*) / \log (L_1 + L_2) \quad (8)$$

where L_1 is the length of the section that is free of bridging fibres, L_2 is length of the section containing bridging fibres, E^* is ratio of E_2 to E_1 that are moduli of the two sections, respectively.

By assigning 60 mm to L_1 , 20 mm to L_2 , variation of n with E^* is given in Table 3:

Table 3 Values of n as a function of E^* for $L_1=60\text{mm}$ and $L_2=20\text{mm}$ in eqn 8.

E^*	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.8	2.0
n	2.98	2.96	2.94	2.93	2.92

As shown in the table, even with an unrealistically large value of 2 for E^* , n does not change much. This suggests that the compliance of the composite is not sensitive to the bridging fibres. Therefore, scattering of n in Table 2 is not due to bridging fibres. The effect of bridging fibres on the increase of G_{IC} is through energy consumption for creation of new fracture surfaces (multiple cracking) and fibre breakage.

CRACK LENGTH MEASUREMENT

The crack length measurement is another source that can cause scattering of the measured G_{IC} values. Accurate measurement of crack length is difficult. De Kalbermatten et al. [9] used in-situ X-ray radiography and acoustic emission to monitor crack growth during delamination testing, from which it was concluded that the crack growth length is always longer in the central region of the specimen than at the edge. Since the crack growth length is measured on the edge of the specimens, the measured value is smaller than that in the centre. This underestimation of crack length has two effects on the G_{IC} values. One is the overestimation of the G_{IC} , directly from calculation using eqns 1 and 2; the other is through increase of the measured n and Δ values (absolute value of Δ decreases). The 2nd effect may also be the cause of the large n values shown in Table 2.

To correct the crack length, the following method is used. We firstly calculated the compliance (C_f) of a given point using the equation:

$$\log C_f = n (\log a_f - \log a_o) + \log C_o \quad (9)$$

with the measured values of n , a_o (initial crack length), a_f (crack length at the point f) and C_o (the compliance at a_o). The C_f obtained was then used to calculate the corrected crack length at point f , $a_{f,corr}$ with the same equation but assigning n to be 2.7. Table 4 lists the G_{IC} values before and after the crack length correction, $G_{IC,exp}$ and $G_{IC,corr}$ respectively. Data were taken from points that had a crack length of approximately 125 mm.

Table 4 Comparison of G_{IC} obtained experimentally and after crack length correction. Numbers in the parentheses are standard deviation of the G_{IC} about the mean values.

Sample #	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Average
$G_{IC,exp}$	743	849	799	988	654	961	685	768	806 (121)
$G_{IC,corr}$	715	865	789	899	630	826	712	806	780 (89)

Table 4 shows that scatter of G_{IC} is improved after the crack length correction. Further work is being carried out to obtain more experimental data to support this method.

CONCLUSIONS

A study was carried out to measure delamination toughness of marine composites. The study showed that the special fibre lay-up employed produced satisfactory results for delamination toughness using the ESIS protocol for interlaminar fracture testing of composites.

Traditional flexural and short beam shear tests results showed little scatter in material properties. However, an unexpectedly large variation of n and Δ was found in the DCB test results, though this variation is not a cause of scatter in G_{IC} . The scatter of G_{IC} is mainly due to variation of the number of bridging fibres at the crack tip and incorrect measurement of crack length.

Two methods were proposed to reduce the G_{IC} scatter. One is based on the difference between the measured Δ value and that estimated from n , the other is based on crack length adjustment using compliance. Both methods allow some reduction in scatter to be obtained, but further work is required to provide experimental support for the methods.

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